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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D7.1 Evaluation Strategy: Psychophysics and Psychometrics observation studies

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Executive Summary

The deliverable 7.1 "Evaluation Strategy: Psychophysics and Psychometrics Observation Studies" outlines a comprehensive approach to evaluating user experience (UX) in the context of image and colour reconstruction. This evaluation strategy is essential for the PERCEIVE project, which aims to advance the state-of-the-art in digital heritage conservation and presentation through innovative AI techniques.

This deliverable focuses specifically on the UX evaluation strategy necessary for the PERCEIVE prototypes, as a preliminary evaluation of prototypes is reported in deliverable 7.2, performed in June at the InArt conference in Oslo. Future updates to this deliverable will include the evaluation strategies of scientific outputs, necessary for consistent colour reproduction, complete with relevant metrics.

Current practices in UX evaluation for image and colour reconstruction are examined in detail, with a focused look at the specific scenarios analysed in PERCEIVE: sculptures, paintings, textiles, photography/film, and digital installations. The strategy provides an in-depth analysis of how UX impacts the perception and appreciation of cultural artifacts enhanced through AI-based colour reconstruction.

The evaluation strategy is tailored to the tools, services, and prototypes (TSP) developed by the partners and uses Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This involves a systematic collection of data on user satisfaction and usability.. The metrics to quantitatively assess the effectiveness of the colour reconstruction and reproduction approaches will be reported in the next version of this deliverable. By doing so, the strategy ensures that the technological advancements meet the needs and expectations of users, thereby enhancing the overall value and impact of the PERCEIVE project's outcomes.

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Introduction

This deliverable reports the PERCEIVE evaluation strategy that falls at the intersection of T7.1 and T7.2

Task 7.1 defines how to assess tools, services and prototypes, and evaluates the relationship between the colour and defined appearance measurements and the individual perceptual experiences, in accordance with specific goals set for each of the TGs (target groups) defined in Section 2.2. Subjective data will be collected through observation studies using techniques from the fields of psychophysics or psychometrics. The increased complexity of newer and future imaging technologies will need more advanced techniques for evaluating different aspects of appearance and image quality, such as evaluating multiple attributes, considering different viewing conditions and the needs of individuals. Similarly, objective measurements are becoming increasingly intricate and multidimensional and novel techniques able to deal with this complexity will be developed.

Custom interfaces will be developed to allow CH practitioners to evaluate and compare the efficacy of the AI-based colour restoration process, related services and tools. Their usability will also be tested. At least 100 reconstructions will be compared on a before/after basis, with additional emphasis being placed in cases where the image quality metrics seem to degrade. Optimal parameter selection ranges will be established and included as part of the pipeline configuration process of T3.4. These results will be supported by specific insights on AI interpretability and visualization through the use of tools like Lucid for neural networks.

1. State-of-the-Art

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

The study of users, their behaviours and their actions, in relation to certain technological devices and contexts, has its theoretical framework in the ethnographic, psychological, and educational research as well as computer science and design rules. In general, the aim is to understand what happens to the individual when using a device or experiencing a context of usage, involves with and records every human gesture and action; the results of this interaction can be used to improve future technological solutions and the experience of the user who will use them.

Evaluations, however, are aimed at analysing not only the product and its context of use; they provide the opportunity to reflect and consider the unforeseen consequences of a system when it is made accessible to the public and the reaction of the latter. Even more relevant, the results and conclusions of evaluations indicate ways to improve the general “cycle of events” related to that product. In other words, evaluation studies should not be conducted for their own sake, but they should be used to support and direct future developments in that particular the research field.

When you conceive a product, especially if it takes into account new technologies and a specific target audience, it is automatic to start thinking about how to evaluate its impact, its usability and its effectiveness, and how this data can help the company or institution that will develop the concept and then the final application, to establish realistic and concrete objectives.

Even more, contents and subjects of the technological-mediated experience are relevant too for scientists and researchers. **What it is challenging is exactly measure and evaluate how such contents are revealed though technological supports; how technology enhances the**

communication of relevant information; how the use of Digital, in general, make accessible cultural data to a broader audience. This is PERCEIVE PROJECT evaluation' goals.

In this way, analyses of the product's production chain are planned, usability pilot tests are carried out, front-end evaluations are started with potential end users, or, again, initial prototypes can be developed (which are accompanied by formal evaluations on usability and effectiveness) and consequently the final product (which is accompanied, instead, by a corrective evaluation on the accessibility of the contents and on the effectiveness). In general, evaluations can be divided into two large categories:

Formative evaluations, which help in the design/planning phase of the idea, and in collecting data that will allow for corrections, already in the design phases, of the user experience and usability; sometimes it can even come before the system design.

Summative evaluations, which are carried out at the end, when the product is ready and helps us provide a quality index of our system with regard to user experience and usability.

There are different evaluation methods that can be adopted. *Qualitative research* (a) identifies abstract concepts while *Quantitative research* (b) collects numerical data. But the substantial difference lies in the type of action applied and the size of the sample (the users investigated). The approaches (a) contemplate an investigated subject who is "passive"; it is therefore an experimental approach since the subject is not reactive, but this does not represent a problem. While the approaches (b) are naturalistic: the user is active and the space and the actions are analysed in the present time, during the development of the research. This clearly greatly influences the work of the researcher who, in case (a), must follow a closed, pre-planned work structure, while in case (b) there is no structure, the approach is open, looking for unexpected options, for unforeseen events, and is modified during the process. Consequently, in qualitative research it is essential and necessary that empathy arises between the two parties, between the user and the researcher, while in quantitative research, the relationship between the two is almost absent: the researcher must be invisible, not very intrusive and must not interact with the user in order not to influence his behaviour and the related responses, both motor and verbal. How to choose the sample of users is also an important aspect in evaluative research: for the qualitative approach, the number of cases investigated is generally limited, by virtue of the fact that they are case-based research, which adopt a holistic perspective of human behaviour, focus on the individual and are therefore very tiring to conduct and long; while in the quantitative one, the number is consistent, as it aims to obtain a strong and generalizable representativeness; in fact, this type of research is called variable-based, it is mostly based on mathematical and statistical techniques, as the nature of the data that is collected is "hard", that is, objective and standardized data.

Clearly the methods chosen to evaluate a product can vary from time to time and can be the result of a mix between the qualitative and quantitative approaches. This is especially in relation to the object of the evaluation, its content, meaning and, in some cases, to its ergonomics. However, there is a clarification to be made: we have spoken several times in this introduction about the evaluation of a product, but in reality, what is evaluated is the experience that the user has of that particular product, as well as its usability. An indicator, for example, is the time that a user takes to perform a task related to that product, or a performance indicator. Questionnaires can instead indicate the user's satisfaction and pleasure in using the product. Therefore, it is plausible that during these evaluations there is always a small margin of error that can easily be reduced if quantitative and qualitative data are integrated.

For some decades, the attention of scholars and researchers in the museum and tourism fields has been focusing on the study and analysis of the impact of multimedia applications and products on the target audience and in relation to urban, indoor and open-air contexts. This is because it has been noted that they are not always sufficiently suited to the interests and needs of end users. The category of users of Digital Cultural Heritage, as well as that of tourists, is particularly demanding when faced with the object of their interest; consequently, these two segments, enthusiasts and users, need products tailored specifically to their experiential needs such as, for example, being on the move, or being in the company of several people, or, again, wanting a customizable service or for a limited time.

Although user experience, or that "discipline" that deals with investigating the intimate relationships that exist between the design characteristics of a product and the emotional and cognitive feedback of the user to whom such a product is subjected, it still finds obstacles in terms of structuring a unique procedural taxonomy to carry out evaluation activities. It is obvious that there is no single investigative methodology because each investigation refers to specific multimedia projects, often very complex and ambitious, which include interaction methods and contents highly tailored to the technological medium used and the destination exhibition location. Furthermore, one of the difficulties in conducting such assessments lies in the multi-disciplinarity of the investigative activity.

As Jeff Johnson, a researcher in the field of experimental psychology, points out, "you cannot create a user experience (user experience), but you can design something so that a user experience occurs. It is not possible to design a satisfying experience, but only to ensure that the ergonomic characteristics of a product can evoke such a sensation" to also guarantee a positive educational response in the user (Johnson, 2010). It is therefore obvious how this area of research pertains various disciplinary sectors: from Social Sciences to Information Design, from Cognitivism to Computer Science. To date, there are few professionals operating in this field, few figures who deal with Cultural Heritage starting from the concept according to which these can be enjoyed in an innovative and spontaneous way thanks to new digital technologies and, consequently, trigger an indirect but equally effective educational mechanism about learning.

Evaluation campaigns in this sense are complex to conduct. Many of the evaluation proposals available today often refer to sectoral or mainly technical investigative objectives: usability tests are very popular, aimed only at studying the structural characteristics of an interactive product, through pre-established evaluation scales; customer satisfaction tests are also becoming more and more frequent, where the primary interest is the quantitative data aimed at identifying a trend of satisfaction. This is certainly not to diminish the importance and effectiveness of such investigations. They are highly useful investigative strategies for the purpose of probing (in broad terms) the relationship between product and user, but they are certainly not sufficient to discover the intimate relationships that exist between them and the relative benefits deriving from the enjoyment of the cultural asset - be it real or virtual - by the user. For this reason, a methodological framework is needed that considers all these factors and proposes a multifaceted and constantly updated investigative model.

In recent years, in research laboratories, universities and at European level, guidelines and operational *vademecum* have been established for evaluation research approaches relating to user experience: they fall within the scope of User Experience Research. In this, the development of interactive and/or immersive media, designed for public places or for exercises, is systematically followed laboratory; the achievement of objectives relating to user experience, usability and accessibility of digital products is measured; finally, the level of attention and the communicative

potential that each individual digital device can convey in ever-changing contexts of use is studied. The ISO 9241-210 standard, for example, has explicitly introduced the User Experience (UX) concept since 2009 in the operating manual of information systems (ISO FDIS 9241-210:2019); the Nielsen Norman Group (NN/g), which has been involved in consultancy in the field of User Interface Design (UID) and User Experience (UX) since the end of the 1990s, has produced countless manuals and tools, accessible online; Hassenzahl was the first in 2008 to produce an evaluation protocol of the emotions that users feel while handling a product (Hassenzahl, M., Burmester, M. & Koller, F., 2021); and like them, others have actively contributed to the discipline.

1.1 Big picture of UX evaluation in Digital Cultural Heritage

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

The evaluation of a digital experience is linked both to **cognitive learning principles**, related to the message that one wants to convey from time to time with respect to a cultural content, and to so-called "**geographic**" **principles**, which concern where, how and how much such multimedia product is used, thus better understanding the underlying technology, its limits and benefits; finally, to an analysis of the **technicalities and usability** of the site-specific multimedia product, created to support and integrate the classic experience of the place chosen for use.

To meet the needs of planning the integrated communication of such multimedia devices, it is first essential to conduct a careful analysis of the **user's requirements**, whether they are a conscious or occasional user. By requirements we mean:

- the **motivations** that push the user to interact with the multimedia application;
- the **criteria for appreciating** or rejecting the multimedia application;
- the **criteria of scientific quality**, narration and usability of the multimedia product.

Each technology obviously implies a universe of specificities, opportunities and limitations especially when content need to be communicated are a stratification of knowledge and research.

In the case of the PERCEIVE PROJECT, we consider **multimedia products such as web application, online and offline tools, Augmented and Mixed Reality devices, tangible interfaces and games** which have a series of features useful for achieving high levels of sensorial and perceptive immersion in the Colours' perception and reconstruction sector.

These technologies certainly allow the implementation of different levels of reading of the cultural information taking advantage of the **interactivity, immersion and playfulness** afforded by these devices, gamification represents an extremely effective tool capable of conveying messages of various types, depending on the needs, and of inducing active behaviours on the part of users, allowing specific educational and enabling objectives to be achieved.

At the centre of this approach is always the user and his active involvement.

The study of the experiential path in which these products are inserted is also relevant, whether they are **outdoor public places or indoor structures** and buildings. This allows for a more unified vision of (a) the ways of enjoying multimedia content, (b) the interaction paradigms that are triggered once the multimedia application is approached, (c) the choices related to the enjoyment of the exhibition space depending on the chosen technology and the methods of interaction, whether it is an open or closed space.

All this largely influences the cognitive system implemented by the user and allows for the analysis of interactive products in relation to their audience, to understand whether they lend themselves to being real “intelligent environments”, contexts capable of conveying a certain cultural information, of stimulating a certain behaviour and, therefore, of actively communicating with their visitors.

1.2 UX evaluation for colour reconstruction

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

The field of evaluations about image quality in colour reconstructions in Heritage Science domain is rapidly evolving, with significant advancements in imaging technologies and computational methods. However, substantial gaps exist, particularly in the areas of standardized evaluation metrics, perceptual fidelity, multimodal data integration, and the impact of aging and degradation.

Addressing these challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach, combining expertise from imaging science, perceptual psychology and cognition, design and ICT as well as heritage conservation.

PERCEIVE evaluation strategy will focus on developing comprehensive, user-centered evaluation frameworks that balance technical accuracy with perceptual quality, ensuring that colour reconstructions not only preserve the technical details of cultural artifacts but also capture their visual and historical essence.

Colour reconstruction in heritage science plays a crucial role in the preservation, restoration, and interpretation of cultural artifacts like textiles, statues, paintings, concrete surfaces as well as digital supports. This field leverages various imaging techniques and computational methods to restore the original appearance of artworks and historical objects, providing invaluable insights into their historical context and significance. However, evaluating the quality of these reconstructions poses significant challenges, as it requires a careful balance between technical accuracy and perceptual fidelity. PERCEIVE PROJECT stands exactly in this intermediate place which reflects the position of internal staff too: a *continuous tension* between conservation scientists and diagnostics on one side, and digital designers and informatics on the other.

In order to identify open issues that PERCEIVE PROJECT might investigate and answer, we first present (1) methodologies and (2) approaches in colours reconstruction for Digital Cultural Heritage, so to arrive to possible (3) gaps to fill in and solutions.

Current Methodologies (1)

- **Multispectral and Hyperspectral Imaging.** These techniques capture information across a wide range of wavelengths, providing detailed spectral data that can be used for accurate colour reconstruction. The evaluation of image quality typically involves comparing the reconstructed colours against reference standards or original pigments using metrics like spectral angle mapper (SAM) and root mean square error (RMSE).
- **Photogrammetry and 3D Imaging.** Photogrammetry and 3D imaging techniques are used to capture the geometry and surface texture of artifacts, which are then combined with colour data to create highly detailed digital models. Image quality evaluation in this context focuses

on the accuracy of colour mapping onto the 3D surface, often assessed through visual inspection and quantitative comparisons.

- **Digital Image Processing.** Various algorithms are employed to enhance and correct colour in digital images of artworks. Techniques include colour constancy algorithms, which adjust for lighting conditions, and inpainting methods, which reconstruct missing or damaged areas. Evaluation metrics for these processes include colour difference formulas, structural similarity index (SSIM), and user studies to assess perceptual quality.

Gaps in Current Approaches (2)

- **Lack of Standardized Evaluation Metrics.** There is no universally accepted set of metrics for evaluating colour reconstruction quality, leading to inconsistent and incomparable results across studies. Existing metrics often do not account for the perceptual aspects of colour, focusing primarily on numerical accuracy. But it is not enough. Quality in colour reconstruction pertains the hedonic sphere, the perceptive and social domains too.
- **Perceptual Fidelity.** Human perception of colours is complex and influenced by numerous factors, including lighting conditions, surface texture, and context. Current methodologies often fail to adequately capture these perceptual nuances, resulting in reconstructions that may be technically accurate but perceptually unsatisfactory.
- **Integration of Multimodal Data.** Combining colour information from different imaging modalities (e.g., multispectral, hyperspectral, and 3D imaging) poses significant challenges. Ensuring consistency and accuracy across these modalities is difficult, and there is a lack of robust frameworks for multimodal data integration and evaluation.
- **Impact of Aging and Degradation.** Artifacts often undergo significant changes in colour over time due to aging and environmental factors. Current evaluation methods do not sufficiently account for these changes, making it difficult to assess the historical accuracy of reconstructions. The latter should be mapped step-by-step, recorded, analyzed and visualized in order to allow reconstructions recalling even after physical restoration or digital intervention.

Open Issues and Future Directions (3)

- Development of Comprehensive Evaluation Frameworks.** There is a need for comprehensive evaluation frameworks that combine technical accuracy with perceptual fidelity. These frameworks should include standardized metrics that reflect both numerical and perceptual aspects of colour quality.
- Advances in Perceptual Modelling.** Improved models of human colour perception are needed to better align technical reconstructions with human visual experience. Integrating these models into evaluation methodologies could enhance the perceptual quality of colour reconstructions. An important aspect to consider is *accessibility*, in terms of visual and perceptive feelings of colours, but also web accessibility for digital products.
- Enhanced Multimodal Integration.** Developing robust methods for integrating colour data from various imaging techniques is crucial. This includes creating algorithms, tools and services that ensure consistency and accuracy across different modalities.

- D. **Consideration of Aging and Degradation.** Future research should focus on methods to account for the effects of aging and environmental degradation on colour. This could involve the development of predictive models, also supported by AI and machine learning techniques that simulate the aging process and its impact on colour.
- E. **User-Centered Approaches.** Incorporating user studies and expert evaluations into the assessment process can provide valuable insights into the perceptual quality of reconstructions. Engaging stakeholders, such as conservators and historians, in the evaluation process, as well as final users like museum public, families and Art passionate can ensure that reconstructions meet the needs and expectations of the heritage community.

PERCEIVE evaluation strategy will try to provide evidence and solutions to all A-to-E open issues.

1.3 State-of-the-art in image quality for colour reconstruction

Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Giorgos Papadopoulos (FORTH), Luuk Wuijster (FORTH)

The following reports a list of metrics used in the field of Digital Restoration of Cultural Heritage (Basu et al., 2023).

Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)

The Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) is a widely used metric for evaluating the perceived quality of reconstructed images. SSIM considers changes in structural information, luminance, and contrast, providing a measure that aligns closely with human visual perception. This metric is particularly useful for assessing the fidelity of colour reconstruction, ensuring that the restored images retain the visual characteristics of the original artifacts.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is another standard metric used to quantify the quality of image reconstruction. PSNR measures the ratio between the maximum possible power of a signal and the power of corrupting noise, expressed in decibels. Higher PSNR values indicate better reconstruction quality. This metric is essential for comparing different reconstruction techniques and ensuring that the reconstructed images are of high fidelity.

Mean Squared Error (MSE)

Mean Squared Error (MSE) calculates the average squared differences between the original and reconstructed images. Although MSE provides a direct measure of reconstruction accuracy, it does not always correlate with perceived visual quality. However, it remains a fundamental metric for evaluating the baseline performance of reconstruction algorithms.

Colour Difference (ΔE)

Colour Difference (ΔE) (Mokrzycki and Tatol, 2011) (Parvathaneni et al., 2024) is a crucial metric for evaluating the accuracy of colour reproduction in reconstructed images. ΔE measures the difference between the colours in the original and reconstructed images using a perceptually uniform colour space, such as CIELAB. This metric is essential for cultural heritage applications, where accurate colour representation is critical.

Commission Internationale d’Eclairage (CIE) proposed various colour difference formulas:

- ΔE was the first one, proposed in 1976
- ΔE_{94} was introduced in 1994, proposing an improvement to the initial ΔE , by adding parametric terms that consider the particularities of a given industry. These two terms are distinct if the colour difference is computed for a textile application, or if it is computed for the graphic art industry.
- ΔE_{00} is a colour difference formula developed to provide a more accurate and perceptually uniform measurement of colour differences. It includes a rotation term to address the problem of the perceptual non-uniformity that occurs for colours in the blue region of the CIELAB space, which was not adequately handled by previous formulas. It incorporates parametric factors to adjust the emphasis on lightness, chroma, and hue differences, providing flexibility for different applications and industries.

Edge Preservation Index (EPI)

The Edge Preservation Index (EPI) assesses the ability of a reconstruction approach to maintain edge details and fine structures. EPI is particularly important for ensuring that the reconstructed images retain the sharpness and structural integrity of the original artifacts. This metric helps in evaluating the effectiveness of reconstruction techniques in preserving important visual features.

Reconstruction Time

Reconstruction Time is a key metric for evaluating the efficiency of machine learning-based colour reconstruction approaches. It measures the time taken to reconstruct an image, which is crucial for practical applications, especially in real-time or large-scale scenarios. Efficient reconstruction algorithms can significantly reduce the time and resources required for processing large datasets.

Resource Utilization

Resource Utilization measures the computational resources, such as memory and CPU/GPU usage, required for the reconstruction process. This metric is essential for assessing the scalability and practicality of reconstruction algorithms. Efficient use of computational resources can lead to cost savings and enable the deployment of these technologies on a larger scale.

User Satisfaction (Subjective Rating)

User Satisfaction is a qualitative metric that collects feedback from cultural heritage professionals and the public on the perceived quality of the reconstructed images. This metric complements quantitative measures by providing insights into the usability and acceptance of the reconstruction tools. High user satisfaction indicates that the tools are effective and meet the needs of end-users.

2. PERCEIVE context of analysis

2.1 What is tool, service and prototype?

Giorgio Trumpy, Irina Ciortan, Yoko Arteaga (NTNU)

To initiate the activities of the task, NTNU asked the collaboration of all partners in mapping the status of tools, services, and prototypes (TSPs) planned for the project. This was achieved with the “so-called” TSP-form, a short-but-crucial document aimed at gathering information about the

development of TSPs. This information enables PERCEIVE to design an appropriate evaluation procedure for each of them.

An empty TSP form is reported in the following.

TSP-form

Deadline Feb 19th, 2024

(check what you describe)

- Tool**
- Service**
- Prototype**

Title (Name of the tool/service/prototype)

Who is in charge? (Reference person and affiliation)

What for? (Description and usefulness referring to specific types of artworks or scenarios)

For whom? (Target group: experts, museum staff, students, or...)

Main functions (Bullet list)

Where can it be experienced? (Multiple choice possible)

- Desktop-based mode (PC)

- Portable device mode (Tablet, mobile phone, etc.)
- Immersive system mode (HMD, cyclorama, cave, hologram, projection, etc.)
- Sensor base mode (Leap motion, Kinect, eye tracking, tangible user interfaces, etc.)
- Other devices or technological supports
- Mixed / Hybrid used

Please, specify: _____

How does it contribute to advancements in the specific field? (please keep it concise)

This tool/service/prototype relates to the following PERCEIVE outcome(s):

- O1 – Know-How webinars and streaming lectures
- O2 – Colour reconstruction methodology and guidelines
- O3 – Tools and guidelines for museums and exhibition/light designers
- O4 – Colour Knowledge Repository
- O5 – PERCEIVE API
- O6 – Colour Reconstruction and Regeneration Service
- O7 – Colour Prediction Service
- O8 – Colour restoration and colourization of B&W images
- O9 – Analytical visualisation
- O10 – Light damage estimator
- O11 – 3D model optimiser
- O12 – web3d multi-texture interactive visualisation editor service
- O13 – Authenticity Prototype
- O14 – Caring Prototype
- O15 – Open Museum Prototype
- O16 – Design Toolbox

Correlation with other tools, services or prototypes (to be developed within PERCEIVE)

What is the level of completeness of your tool/service/prototype?

- Only concept & design
- Work-in-progress version
- Full-functioning version

Pipeline of work for the development

Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5
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(short description)				
Ready by (date)				
__/__/__	__/__/__	__/__/__	__/__/__	__/__/__

How will the tool/service/prototype be created?

- Prototyping language (e.g., Python, Matlab, VVVV, Figma)

Please, specify: _____

- High-end language (e.g., C++, Java)

Please, specify: _____

- Physical development and manufacturing

Please, specify: _____

- Other

Please, specify: _____

Do you identify potential collaborators? (In the PERCEIVE consortium or elsewhere)

- No
- Yes

Please, specify name and/or institution: _____

What is it necessary to assess for your tool/service/prototype? (Multiple choice possible)

User experience of people using the tool/service/prototype

- Interaction with the system (Nielsen/Norman principles)
- Aesthetical aspects of the system (Visibility)
- Cognitive sphere (Attention, memorization and elaboration of the user experience)

Other, please specify _____

Tool/service/prototype main features

- Usability of the system
- Output accuracy (i.e., image quality, metrics....)
- Appearance consistency across imaging technologies
- Other, please specify _____

Every TSP-form was filled in and signed by the reference person.

Once all the filled TSP-forms were collected, an overview of all tools, services, and prototypes was built.

Title	Type	Reference person	Description	Target group	Main functions	Input/Output	Experience mode	Innovation	Related outcomes	Related tools, services and/or prototypes	Collaborators	Assessment	Release
Light Damage Estimator (D16)	Tool	Sopha Sotiriadou (PORTH) Panagiotis Sotiropoulos (PORTH)	The 'Estimation tool of Light-induced color degradation' is a sophisticated tool designed to assist professionals in assessing the potential impact of lighting on the color of an artwork. This tool employs advanced simulation techniques to predict and visualize the distribution of individual colors or colors within artworks under different lighting conditions. Key features of the Light Damage Estimator include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation Capabilities: The tool offers specific algorithms and models to accurately simulate how different types of lighting (such as natural light, incandescent, LED, etc.) will affect the colors of an artwork over time. Customization Options: Professionals can specify the parameters of the lighting conditions, including intensity, duration, and spectral composition, allowing for precise and scenario simulation. Color Analysis: The tool provides detailed analysis of the color changes, allowing professionals to understand the extent of degradation and potential restoration needs. 	Museum professionals (curators, conservators, exhibition teams), banks with museums/galleries, insurance for the illumination of artworks, or in charge of assessing the light sensitivity of the artwork and materials of the artwork, with a specific focus on colorants.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimation of illumination impact Simulation of color degradation Prediction of fading losses for the illumination of artworks Functionality with paintings and 2D artworks Use of hyperspectral imaging and laboratory data Web, web-based access 	Input: Output:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desktop-based mode Portable device mode 	The development of PERCEIVE: 'Estimation tool of Light-induced color degradation' is included in this context to offer a specific method to assess the influence of lighting on the colors of artworks and simulate potential color deterioration under different lighting scenarios. The objective is to design a tool capable of reflecting the calculation of authentic light impacts and offering an assessment of the impact of lighting on potential damage, considering the specific emission spectra profile of a chosen illumination system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The specific tool is already applied to the: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Color Reconstruction and Regeneration Service (CR) Color Prediction Service (CS) Analytical visualization tool (AV) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HELIX (BNC) PORTH robotics lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interaction with the system Aesthetic aspects of the system Usability of the system Output accuracy 	4/17/23	
Analytical Visualization Service (D9)	Tool, Service and Prototype	Sopha Sotiriadou (PORTH) Panagiotis Sotiropoulos (PORTH)	The Analytical Visualization Service provides tools for the visual representation of non-visible ranging or non-visible analytical information derived from the scientific investigation of an artwork. Visualizations can be realized in different ways, either as overlays on the visible reference digital image of the researched object (e.g. as a map of spectral responses), by isolating colorings or filtering or partial coverage masking (CM) as in a false color visualization as by means of animation options accompanied with related data or documentation.	As a tool to show data to professionals from museum, color scientists and students in conservation/science for Art and Conservation as well as the general public.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overlay images obtained with different remote imaging techniques or in different spectral bands Projecting a sequence of processed images Overlay of spectral images Spectral demarcation of areas of interest or areas of analysis Measuring CMs Mapping areas based on specific characteristics or other (coloring/segmentation) Animation Alternative visualization systems Interactive functions 	Input: Output:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desktop-based mode Portable device mode Interactive system mode CloudHybrid 	The main advancement is an easier and image-based way of displaying complex scientific concepts related to the change of color and appearance of an artwork. It can also be part of predictive systems or tools knowledge not available to conservation and museum professionals.	see related outcomes	All partners contributing with data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interaction with the system Aesthetic aspects of the system Cognitive aspects Usability of the system Output accuracy Appearance consistency 	30/09/2024	
Color reconstruction of Intesticular Kodachrome film	Tool	George Trunpy (INTHE) Sopha Sotiriadou (PORTH)	The tool allows to reconstruct the color of an Intesticular film, also Kodachrome. The digital color reconstruction process involves the creation of a color calibration chart that is spatially encoded in the photographic emulsion. The tool overcomes the technological obsolescence of this type of color film, whose original visualization is impractical since the imaging projection equipment is hard to find.	Art collectors Private collectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application scenarios: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Label the film scan index file or image sequence Label the color reconstruction of the Intesticular boundaries Extraction of the RGB colors Further processing to improve image quality Output the color video codes file or image sequence 	Input: Gray-scale image Output: RGB image	Desktop-based mode	Kodachrome is a little known color process. This film risk to be classified as "black and white" by film archives and collectors, which is actually contains color information. There are only a couple of service providers around the world that do color reconstruction. It is necessary to raise awareness about this color process to save the film name process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A prototype designed in collaboration with HELIX and Kinetograph Lab (BNC) to develop a digital version of the prototype and release the tool publicly with users. 	All partners contributing to the data labelling, HELIX for the prototype, BNC to develop a digital version of the prototype and release the tool publicly with users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability of the system Output accuracy 	30/09/2024	

Fig. 1 A screenshot of the online spreadsheet “TSP overview” containing all the collected TSP-forms

We collected 21 TSP forms in total, where 37% were tools, 37% services, and 26% prototypes. In the process of collecting the forms, we found the need of defining the terminology of tools, services, and prototypes. The proposed definitions are:

- **PERCEIVE Tool:** It is a single-method function, designed to perform a specific task, not visible to the end user. It has a clear input and output, where the output is individually assessed (qualitatively and quantitatively). Can be used in multiple services or prototypes. PERCEIVE tools are part of the PERCEIVE platform.

- PERCEIVE Service: A combination of tools and other functionalities. The input and output can vary, and the output is not strictly necessary. It can be scenario specific or scenario agnostic.
- PERCEIVE Prototype: Museum application intended to communicate a concept to the public. It is a combination of tools, services and user-friendly interface. It is a preliminary version of a concept, created to test and evaluate its design, functionality, and feasibility. The final version of the prototype can be included in a demo version.

Following the proposed definitions above, the updated numbers of PERCEIVE tools, services, and prototypes are 63%, 21% and 16% respectively.

UX evaluation Strategy: goals and metrics

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC), Giorgos Papadopoulos (FORTH), Luuk Wuijster (FORTH)

The PERCEIVE project aims to provide a comprehensive picture on the way colour is understood, managed, and communicated within Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Art by **common users, professionals and stakeholders and policy makers**.

The general goals of the project are:

- (A) **increase the “sense of wonder” for coloured collections and develop a sense of “care”;**
- (B) **train visitors' perception to promote better understanding of coloured collections and bring an awareness of the scientific process behind;**
- (C) **strengthen “authenticity” in remote experiences;**
- (D) **widen access through participation.**

This strategy outlines the user experience (UX) approach, focusing on the seamless integration and optimization of **user interaction, satisfaction, and long-term platform engagement**, driven by key performance indicators (KPIs) outlined under the Grant Agreement, and translated into **UX indicators (UXi)**.

Leveraging an interdisciplinary approach, PERCEIVE states that it “*will establish a comprehensive framework for capturing, processing, assessing, representing, communicating, and reproducing colour images*”; this means that the capability of tools, services and prototypes developed within the project should be **tested, monitored and finally assessed** by means of periodical surveys, beta-testing sessions and practical uses.

Within the PERCEIVE project would be useful to highlight the evaluation stage each tool, prototype and service undergoes as presented in the table below.

<i>Evaluation stage</i>	<i>Activity</i>		
Test / Beta -Test	<input type="checkbox"/> To do	<input type="checkbox"/> Doing	<input type="checkbox"/> Done
Monitoring	<input type="checkbox"/> To do	<input type="checkbox"/> Doing	<input type="checkbox"/> Done
Final assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> To do	<input type="checkbox"/> Doing	<input type="checkbox"/> Done

3.1 UX indicators (UXi)

<p>UXi 1</p>	<p>User-Centered research and design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Stakeholder engagement:</i> Conduct comprehensive stakeholder mapping to include both cultural institutions and creative companies. This includes collaborating with the Advisory Board (AB) to select a diverse range of participants for the PERCEIVE tool testing. • <i>Targeted user research:</i> Engage directly with museum curators, conservators, and CH practitioners to understand their unique needs, workflows, and preferences. Conduct interviews, surveys, and workshops to gather insights particularly around colour communication in digital formats. • <i>Personas:</i> Develop detailed user personas for cultural institutions and creative companies to align experiences with user goals and expectations, also representing museum visitors, remote audiences, designers, and educators to understand their needs and contexts. • <i>Visitor journey mapping:</i> Map visitor journeys through both physical and virtual spaces to pinpoint moments of interaction and engagement, ensuring that each step enhances the understanding and enjoyment of colored collections. • <i>Accessibility and inclusivity:</i> Incorporate accessibility standards to make exhibits, scientific contents and technologies usable for a broad audience, including those with varying levels of digital familiarity or physical disabilities. 	<p>actions in WP1, WP2, WP6, WP8</p>
<p>UXi 2</p>	<p>Clear, intuitive interfaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Simplicity and clarity:</i> Design an interface that balances aesthetic appeal with functional clarity. Prioritize easy-to-navigate layouts to minimize learning curves and enhance user satisfaction. • <i>Guided onboarding:</i> Implement a guided onboarding process to familiarize users with technology features and provide context around PERCEIVE’s value. • <i>Feature discoverability:</i> Design intuitive paths and cues for users to explore additional tools and services, helping them uncover the full scope of what the platform offers. 	<p>actions in WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6</p>
<p>UXi 3</p>	<p>Feedback loops and iterative design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Prototyping and testing:</i> Test early-stage prototypes with targeted groups in labs and from both the cultural sector and creative companies. Collect feedback to validate design decisions and make improvements. • <i>Usability testing:</i> Conduct regular usability testing sessions to monitor user satisfaction and pinpoint any issues with navigation, comprehension, and functionality. • <i>Continuous improvement:</i> Adopt an agile methodology to iteratively improve platform functionality and UX based on user feedback and KPI metrics. 	<p>actions in WP5, WP6</p>

<p>UXi 4</p>	<p>Educational toolkit and interactive design tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Toolkit for designers and professionals:</i> Develop a set of design tools that digital designers, digital curators and museum professionals can use to create customized, interactive experiences that align with specific educational goals. • <i>Guided templates and resources:</i> Provide templates, frameworks, and step-by-step guides for setting up digital applications, reducing the time and cost associated with exhibit development. • <i>Hands-on training and workshops:</i> Offer online and in-person training sessions to familiarize users with the toolkit, encouraging adoption and maximizing the toolkit’s effectiveness. 	<p>actions in WP2, WP6, WP8</p>
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All PERCEIVE UXi will be achieved employ a **multi-partitioned analysis** as operational methodology (Pagano et al., 2016), involving:

1. **Quantitative metrics:** the planned evaluations will track key usage statistics, including user retention, engagement rates, feature adoption, and task success rates across cultural and creative sectors.
2. **Qualitative feedback:** user satisfaction surveys, focus groups, and AB feedback will provide qualitative data to gauge user satisfaction and identify areas for improvement.
3. **Longitudinal studies:** track and analyse engagement trends over time to assess whether changes in tools, services and prototypes occur and how they positively impact long-term user adoption and satisfaction.
4. **Case Studies and success stories:** Document user case studies to measure the tools, prototypes and services impact on curatorial practices, using them to promote PERCEIVE’s success and further motivate CH adoption.

For more details see [DEL7.2](#).

3.2 KPIs and Strategy Breakdown

OB1.

Make heritage science results accessible for immediate use and further development to Creative Industry sectors, including Computer Graphics specialists, Exhibition and Light Designers, Game companies.

Ensure the tools, services and prototypes success across cultural institutions, creative companies, and broader business contexts. Each KPI of OB1 directs specific UX activities, methodologies, and metrics to align user experiences with the project's goals.

KPI_OB1

<p>KPI 1.1</p>	<p>Number of cultural institutes reached</p>	<p>Based on PERCEIVE Call measure and in accordance with Advisory Board (AB) guidelines, a set of cultural institutes are selected for testing Tools, Services and Prototypes.</p>	<p>≥ 20</p>
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KPI 1.2	Number of creative companies reached	Based on the PERCEIVE Call and AB guidelines, a set of creative sector companies will be contacted for testing Tools, Services and Prototypes. At least 5 companies will be selected for testing the tools.	≥ 100 SMEs
KPI 1.3	Business Potential	Business potential of the PERCEIVE outcomes, in € for the next 10 years, in terms of: new business, improved market share and improved efficiency and profitability.	≥ € 10M
KPI 1.4	Platform Engagement Score (similar to Pendo PES)	Measurement of the engagement of PERCEIVE’s Platform (and Repository), in terms of platform’s Adoption (percentage of stakeholders that use PERCEIVE’s features), Stickiness (reusability of features) and Growth (exploitation expansion).	≥ 70%

UX Strategy KPI Breakdown

KPI 1.1	Number of cultural institutes reached	≥ 20	<p>Targeted outreach: Partner with the AB to engage cultural institutes in testing the platform. Develop clear, value-focused outreach materials emphasizing the benefits for colours revealing studies and colour communication in digital cultural heritage.</p> <p>Engagement incentives: Offer participation incentives, such as exclusive insights or benefits, to encourage active involvement in the tools, prototypes and services testing.</p>
			<p>Metrics: Track the number of cultural institutes reached and their level of engagement with PERCEIVE’s tools and prototypes, both by direct contact with them or as autonomous action of reaching out to PERCEIVE project, partners or initiatives.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. of cultural institutes hosting PERCEIVE exhibitions • Nr. of cultural institutes collaborating with the development of PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes • Nr. of cultural institutes hosting or lending professionals and students for PERCEIVE case studies • Nr. of cultural institutes involved in PERCEIVE as external consultants • Nr. of cultural institutes participating at PERCEIVE webinars, workshops, round tables... • Nr. of cultural institutes involved in PERCEIVE formative programmes • Nr. of cultural institutes using PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes as final users
KPI 1.2	Number of creative	≥ 100 SMEs	<p>Sector-specific customization: Tailor experiences to the creative sector with modules that resonate with their workflows, <i>e.g.</i> colour correction, visualization, 3D printing, physical scenography, and creative asset management.</p>

	companies reached		<p>Engagement incentives: Facilitate workshops, round tables and open labs to actively involve creative companies, demonstrating the project potential for enhancing creative processes.</p> <p>Metrics: Monitor the number of creative companies reached and their active use of tools, prototypes and services.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. of CCIs collaborating with the development of PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes • Nr. of CCIs participating at PERCEIVE webinars, workshops, round tables... • Nr. of CCIs involved in PERCEIVE formative programmes • Nr. of CCIs using PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes as final users
KPI 1.3	Business Potential	≥ € 10M	n.d.
KPI 1.4	Platform Engagement Score (similar to Pendo PES)	≥ 70%	<p>Feature adoption analysis: Monitor the adoption rates of different features, ensuring essential tools are accessible and appealing. Adjust design elements to boost adoption where usage is lower.</p> <p>Content reusability: Emphasize reusable elements such as templates, custom workflows, and saved settings that encourage frequent interaction.</p> <p>Growth focus: Regularly update the tools, prototypes and services with enhancements based on user insights to support sustainable growth and retention.</p> <p>Metrics: Calculate an engagement score based on adoption, feature stickiness, and growth metrics, aiming for a 70% engagement rate.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. of active users who have accessed PERCEIVE’s platform within a defined period • Percentage of new users over the total user base, showing user acquisition over time • Number of times users return to the platform within a month or quarter • Average time spent on the platform per session • Number of users who repeatedly use platform features (e.g., digital restoration tools, VR/AR interactions, exhibit design tools) • Percentage of users who return to the same features multiple times, indicating high user engagement with specific tools

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average number of actions a user takes within a feature, highlighting deep engagement • Nr. of saved or exported projects • Percentage of users interacting with multiple features, suggesting they explore various parts of the platform • Number of projects that involve multiple users or institutions, indicating network growth and collaboration
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OB2.

Improve museums curatorial approaches to the study of coloured collection through digital shared methodology and to the use of digital practices to exhibit them (making conservation science results accessible so that they can be used for purposes of curation, preservation, and exhibition by developing a common and shareable protocol for investigation and reconstruction, leading to a new digital empowerment in museums).

Achieving KPIs for OB2 by ensuring PERCEIVE’s tools, services, and methodologies are user-friendly, accessible, and applicable for CH stakeholders, particularly museums. By supporting curatorial, preservation, and exhibition practices, this strategy will foster adoption, usability, and cost-effectiveness, empowering museums to integrate digital practices seamlessly into their work.

KPI_OB2

KPI 2.1	Number of involved CH stakeholders	Refers to the number of museums and other CH parties that are using PERCEIVE’s tools and services for designing and executing curatorial activities.	≥ 20
KPI 2.2	Number of ICT tools adopted	Refers to the number of PERCEIVE’s Tools and Services that are used by CH stakeholders.	≥ 5
KPI 2.3	Number accesses to Guidelines and training	Refers to the number of downloads/online to PERCEIVE guidelines and know-how online training	≥ 200
KPI 2.4	Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of an activity’s required process time (e.g. exhibition design or photorealistic 3D rendering), by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE features.	≥ 60%
KPI 2.5	Cost Reduction	Refers to the reduction of an activity’s cost (e.g. exhibition design or photorealistic 3D rendering), by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE features.	≥ 40%

UX Strategy KPI Breakdown

KPI 2.1	Number of involved CH stakeholders	≥ 20	Targeted outreach and engagement: Develop campaigns to inform museums and CH organizations about PERCEIVE’s benefits, focusing on digital empowerment for preservation and curation.
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			<p>Showcase success stories: Share case studies of early adopters to demonstrate the platform’s value, motivating other institutions to engage with PERCEIVE.</p> <p>Metrics: Track the number of museums and CH organizations actively using the tools, prototypes and services for curatorial and preservation tasks.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nr. of cultural institutes collaborating with the development of PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes Nr. of cultural institutes using PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes as final users
KPI 2.2	Number of ICT tools adopted	≥ 5	<p>Feature prioritization: Ensure the design of high-demand tools (e.g., colour analysis, photorealistic 3D rendering) is accessible and easily adoptable.</p> <p>Modular and scalable design: Present the tools as modular features that users can adopt gradually, with clear tutorials and guidelines to support incremental adoption.</p> <p>Metrics: Measure tools, prototypes and services usage and adoption rates, aiming to have at least 5 tools widely used by CH stakeholders.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nr. of tools used by cultural institutes Nr. of services used by cultural institutes Nr. of prototypes used by cultural institutes
KPI 2.3	Number accesses to Guidelines and training	≥ 200	<p>Resource visibility: Ensure training materials and guidelines are prominently accessible through PERCEIVE’s platform, with clear labelling and categorized resource pages.</p> <p>Promotional campaigns: Develop targeted outreach to encourage downloads and online usage of PERCEIVE’s guidelines and training resources, including webinars and live sessions.</p> <p>Metrics: Track access statistics, downloads, and usage metrics for guidelines and training materials to meet the goal of 200 accesses.</p> <p>Index to track (analytics):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nr. of unique users accessing guidelines and training materials Total page views for guidelines and training materials Access frequency per user Nr. of downloads of guidelines Nr. of downloads of training materials Repeat downloads Average time spent on guidelines and training pages

- Completion rate of training sessions (*if applicable*): Percentage of users who complete online training sessions, showing user engagement and effectiveness of training material.
- Active engagement during sessions: Counts interactions within training materials, highlighting active participation.
- Nr. of feedback submissions or ratings for guidelines and training
- Where users are finding the guidelines and training, identifying successful dissemination channels (e.g., referral from partners, search engines, direct link).
- Geographic and demographic reach
- Engagement from target groups (e.g., cultural institutes, professionals, general public)
- Monthly progress toward 200-access goal
- Comparison to previous periods

KPI 2.4	Time Reduction	≥ 60%	n.d.
KPI 2.5	Cost Reduction	≥ 40%	n.d.

OB3.

Improve colour reconstruction and prediction methodologies and workflow (reliable natural perception, colour reconstruction, light transfer and colour change prediction).

Measuring advancements in colour accuracy, prediction reliability, workflow efficiency, and user satisfaction. Each UXi will allow PERCEIVE to comprehensively monitor improvements in colour reconstruction, prediction reliability, workflow efficiency, and overall user satisfaction, ensuring the methodologies meet high standards in accuracy and practicality for cultural heritage applications.

KPI_OB3

KPI 3.1	Reconstruction fidelity/quality	Quantitative evaluation of the restoration/ recolorisation output by using Image Quality Assessment metrics: Structural Similarity (SSIM) and Blocking Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR-B).	SSIM: ≥ 0.9 PSNR-B: ≥ 45dB
KPI 3.2	Reconstruction Subjective Rating	Empirical evaluation of the quality/ fidelity of the predicted restored artwork, carried out by specialist stakeholders.	≥ 90%
KPI 3.3	Reconstruction Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of a colour reconstruction process' required time, by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE Framework.	≥ 60%

KPI 3.4	Number of simulated scenarios	Refers to colour simulation applications that will be provided to CH stakeholders through the PERCEIVE platform.	≥ 3
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UX Strategy KPI Breakdown

KPI 3.1	Reconstruction fidelity/quality	SSIM: ≥ 0.9 PSNR-B: ≥ 45dB	n.d.
KPI 3.2	Reconstruction Subjective Rating	≥ 90%	n.d.
KPI 3.3	Reconstruction Time Reduction	≥ 60%	n.d.
KPI 3.4	Number of simulated scenarios	≥ 3	<p>Metrics:</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PERCEIVE is working on n.5 scenarios, which involved the stakeholders and AB in the definitions of priorities and needs, and define how to refine them to better develop PERCEIVE solutions. Specific tools, services and prototypes are then designed and developed. Up to now we have: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Disappearing or Lost Polychromy 2. Change of colors in paintings and works on paper 3. Fading colors in Textiles (dresses and tapestry) 4. Fading colors in Photographic collections 5. Perceiving and Preserving colors in Born Digital Artworks • Nr. of lighting scenarios simulated used to test reconstructions, ensuring robustness under diverse environments • Nr. of different materials (e.g., textiles, ceramics, paint) reconstructed, ensuring versatility across artifact types • Nr. of environmental conditions simulated to test reconstruction stability, assessing model robustness • Counts various complexity levels, such as intricate patterns or rare colorations, that have been accurately reconstructed, demonstrating flexibility and scope

OB4.

Widen the access and exploration of the use of coloured collections (and their restoration) and digital artworks, involving visitors and citizens (inside but also outside museums), improving their understanding and at the same time increasing their engagement with experiences that could be perceived as “authentic”.

OB4 aims to provide a seamless, engaging and accessible experience through interactive tools, VR/AR experiences, and hybrid digital-physical exhibits, while achieving KPIs related to public engagement, cost reduction, and commercial outcomes. This approach ensures that the UX is accessible to designers, educators, and visitors alike, optimizing the reach and effectiveness of PERCEIVE’s offerings.

KPI_OB4

KPI 4.1	Nr of prototypes	Refers to the nr of prototypes designed in the project and ready to be tested	≥ 3
KPI 4.2	Nr of Design Tools	Refers to the nr of design tools in the toolkit ready to be used by designers and educators	≥ 3
KPI 4.3	Nr of users	Refers to the number of downloads or participants testing prototypes and toolkit in events or on line sessions	≥ 200
KPI 4.4	Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of time needed to set up a digital application or develop a digital exhibit	by 60%
KPI 4.5	Cost Reduction	Refers to the reduction of costs due to the speeding of the process from ideation to market ready product creation (The European exhibition market size is expected to reach revenues of \$18 billion by 2025, growing at a CAGR of over 3% during the forecast period. However, the cost of a media exhibition is quite expensive (i.e. from 5K€ to 15K€ per m ² for a large media exhibition) and with COVID Impact, the profitability of a cultural exhibition is more and more complicated.	$\geq 25\%$
KPI 4.6	Increased public attendance	PERCEIVE's VR/AR technologies will help maintain participation. Moreover, the introduction of HYBRID coloured experiences where the physical and digital components are integrated would increase the innovation appeal of exhibitions and creative products in general	$\geq 80\%$
KPI 4.7	Commercialisation of project outcomes and increase of revenues	PERCEIVE is a strong competitive differentiation in cultural areas. The company Museum Factory wants to commercialize PERCEIVE results with licensing to their customers. As an example, one of the partners, the Museum Factory group including ANAMNESIA, a French leading company in cultural exhibitions, plans to increase annual revenues. This first exploitation, with other partner companies, demonstrates the interest of such an innovative solution in the cultural sector. This could also be deployed internationally for a large exploitation, and societal and economical impacts.	$\geq 15\%$

UX Strategy KPI Breakdown

KPI 4.1	<p>Nr of prototypes (fig.X)</p>	<p>≥ 3</p>	<p>Diverse prototyping: Develop at least three distinct prototypes targeting different engagement modes, such as VR/AR experiences, mobile applications, and interactive installations, to test a variety of user interactions.</p> <p>Iterative testing and feedback: Regularly test these prototypes with small user groups to refine functionality and usability.</p> <p>Metrics: Track the number of prototypes developed and their progression through various testing phases. <i>See WP6 outcomes.</i></p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. of PP developed by CNR (MulaX, Perceptive Multi-Sensory Exploration of the Sanctuary of Isis...) • Nr. of PP developed by FRAUNHOFER(hybrid installation on the Temple of Isis in Pompeii, ...) • Nr. of PP developed by HLSU (Authochrome, VR Coma, The Scream Demonstrator, The Aljosa Box, Space Art Gallery Demonstrator) • Nr. of PP developed by MUCH (Echoes of Munch: A Family Adventure) • Nr. of PP developed by NTNU • Nr. of PP developed by FOTH • Nr. of PP developed by ANAMNESIA •
KPI 4.2	<p>Nr of Design Tools</p>	<p>≥ 3</p>	<p>Targeted toolkit features: Design tools within the toolkit to meet specific needs of exhibit designers and educators, focusing on interactive content creation, colour management, and digital storytelling.</p> <p>Interactive and easy-to-use interfaces: Ensure the toolkit is intuitive and allows users to create and customize exhibits with minimal technical knowledge.</p> <p>Metrics: Measure the number of design tools developed and their adoption rates among CH stakeholders.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. and type of TOOL developed by CNR • Nr. of CCIs using such tools • Nr. of cultural institutes using such tools •
KPI 4.3	<p>Nr of users</p>	<p>≥ 200</p>	<p>Active promotion and outreach: Run campaigns to encourage museums, designers, and educators to download or participate in online testing sessions and events.</p> <p>Community building and support: Create forums or online communities where users can exchange ideas, share tips, and discuss best practices, fostering engagement and community learning.</p>

			<p>Metrics: Track the number of downloads and active participants in testing sessions and events to meet a target of 200 users</p> <p>Index to track:</p>
KPI 4.4	Time Reduction	by 60%	n.d.
KPI 4.5	Cost Reduction	≥ 25%	n.d.
KPI 4.6	Increased public attendance	≥ 80%	<p>Hybrid and interactive experiences: Design experiences that combine physical and digital components to increase the public engagement.</p> <p>VR/AR immersiveness: Use immersive technologies to create engaging experiences that attract a wide audience, including remote visitors.</p>
			<p>Metrics: Analyse attendance data pre- and post-implementation to measure increases in public attendance and engagement.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average attendance per PERCEIVE event or exhibit in each location • Average attendance of each location without PERCEIVE initiative (control group) • Average time spent by visitors in PERCEIVE exhibits (Oslo, Lucerne, Naples,and others) • Nr. of visitor participating in interactive experiences • Nr. of interactions per visitor (VR/AR usage, digital access...) • Post-visit feedback or surveys completed
KPI 4.7	Commercialisation of project outcomes and increase of revenues	≥ 15%	n.d.

2024

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|--|--|--|
| September 2024
Color rectification of artworks' images on chromogenic film |
| September 2024
Color-mosaic/silver-image layer separation for Autochromes |
| September 2024
Pan-/Ortho-chromatization of Hyperspectral cubes |
| June 2024
Light Damage Estimator (O10) | |
| August 2024
2D Inpainting Service | |
| September 2024
Color rectification of artworks' images on chromogenic film | |

2025

- **January 2025**
Data Repository
Perceive API
- **September 2025**
Creative Engagement Based Caring Prototype
- **September 2025**
Caring Prototype Kinetic Module

TBD

- Web3D Multitexture visualization
- AI colorization of black and white painting photographs
- Style Transfer Service
- 3D Model Optimizer
- Time slider for paintings

2026

- **January 2026**
Co-design Tool

List of OUTCOMES: supposed tools, services and prototypes developed within PERCEIVE project timeline.

OB5.

European Citizens re-appropriation of Coloured Collections, increasing awareness of their fragility and importance, through the development of “sense of care”, based on the sense of wonder, emotion and embodiment.

OB5 seeks to facilitate an emotional and immersive experience for citizens, promoting both awareness and a “sense of care” for cultural heritage. By aligning with KPI factors related to participation and engagement, the UX strategy aims to ensure a broad reach among the public, while nurturing a meaningful connection that leads to lasting impact and advocacy for preservation efforts.

KPI_OB5

KPI 5.1	Increased participation	It refers to the numbers of testing users of the prototypes among users of different targets, but also among professionals and decision makers to analyse the potential impact on future decisions (such as on increase of interest and funding campaigns toward preservation/restoration)	≥ 200
KPI 5.2	Development of sense of care	It refers to parameters of engagement and sense of care identified during the project and evaluated in the assessment tasks. Analysis regarding the engagement will be defined and used as reference for this KPI	≥ 30%

UX Strategy KPI Breakdown

KPI 5.1	Increase d participation	≥ 200	<p>Outreach and accessibility: Conduct public awareness campaigns to attract a broad audience, including educational groups, museum visitors, both online and in person.</p> <p>Engagement Events: Host events, such as “hands-on” digital conservation sessions and educational webinars, that allow citizens and professionals alike to interact with the prototypes.</p>
			<p>Metrics: Track participant numbers across different target groups, aiming for a minimum of 200 engaged users testing the prototypes, including both citizens and professionals.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nr. of users visiting PERCEIVE exhibitions • Nr. of users collaborating with the development of PERCEIVE tools, services and prototypes through beta-testing in Labs • Nr. of users participating at PERCEIVE webinars, workshops, round tables • Nr. of users participating at UX evaluation during InArt exhibit and workshop in Oslo, MUNCH, June 2024 (<i>see D7.2 and specific report</i>) • Nr. of users participating at UX evaluation during Parcour exhibit in Lucerne, HLSU, December 2024 • Nr. of users participating at UX evaluation during Digital Heritage Conference in Siena, September 2025 • Nr. of users participating at UX evaluation during final PERCEIVE exhibit in Naples, November 2025
KPI 5.2	Development of sense of care	≥ 30%	<p>Evaluative surveys and emotional metrics: After interactions, gather data on users’ emotional responses and self-reported sense of care through short surveys and feedback forms.</p> <p>Engagement analysis: Measure deeper levels of engagement, such as time spent on preservation simulations, interactions with storytelling elements, and follow-up actions, to gauge a genuine sense of care.</p>

			<p>Reflective content prompts: Include prompts that encourage reflection on the artwork’s preservation needs, increasing the likelihood of users developing a sense of responsibility.</p> <p>Metrics: Analyse survey responses and engagement metrics to ensure that at least 30% of users express an increased sense of care.</p> <p>Index to track:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback of users participating at general CARE evaluation, Bologna, December 2024 • Feedback of users participating at InArt exhibit and workshop in Oslo, MUNCH, June 2024 (<i>see D7.2 and specific report</i>) • Feedback of users participating at UX evaluation during Parcour exhibit in Lucerne, HLSU, December 2024 • Feedback of users participating at UX evaluation during final PERCEIVE exhibit in Naples, November 2025
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3.2 Focus on: Metrics for quantitative evaluation of machine learning based colour reconstruction approaches

The PERCEIVE project aims to innovate the field of cultural heritage conservation by developing advanced tools and technologies for colour reconstruction. The accurate restoration of colours in digital representations of cultural artifacts is crucial for their preservation and interpretation.

To ensure the effectiveness and accuracy of the machine learning-based colour reconstruction approaches within the PERCEIVE project, a comprehensive set of metrics has been proposed. These metrics encompass traditional evaluation measures and domain-specific metrics tailored to the unique requirements of cultural heritage preservation.

Colour reconstruction in the context of cultural heritage is a multifaceted challenge that requires a balance between technical precision, perceptual accuracy, and practical applicability. The integrity of colour in digital representations is vital for the preservation, study, and public appreciation of cultural artifacts. Therefore, robust evaluation metrics are essential to assess and enhance the performance of colour reconstruction tools. This section outlines the proposed metrics that will be employed in the PERCEIVE project to ensure that the reconstructed images meet the highest standards of fidelity, efficiency, and user satisfaction.

Colour Difference (ΔE) [KPI 3.1]:

The Colour Difference (ΔE) metric is pivotal for evaluating the accuracy of colour reproduction in reconstructed images. Implemented in PERCEIVE, the ΔE metric quantifies the perceptual difference between the original and reconstructed colours, ensuring high fidelity in colour restoration. The formulas for ΔE vary depending on the version used, including ΔE₇₆, ΔE₉₄, and ΔE₀₀, each with increasing complexity to better model perceptual differences. The general formula for ΔE₇₆ is:

$$\Delta E_{76} = \sqrt{(L_2 - L_1)^2 + (a_2 - a_1)^2 + (b_2 - b_1)^2}$$

This metric is particularly relevant for cultural heritage applications where accurate colour representation is critical to preserving the integrity and authenticity of artifacts.

Edge Preservation Index (EPI) [KPI 3.1]:

The Edge Preservation Index (EPI) is employed to assess the ability of a reconstruction approach to maintain edge details and fine structures. In the context of PERCEIVE, EPI is calculated as follows:

$$EPI = \frac{\sum_{i,j} |I_{original}(i,j) - I_{reconstructed}(i,j)|}{\sum_{i,j} |I_{original}(i,j)|}$$

This metric is crucial for ensuring that the reconstructed images retain the sharpness and structural integrity of the original artifacts, which is essential for the visual integrity of cultural heritage items.

Reconstruction Time [KPI 3.3]:

Reconstruction Time is a key metric for evaluating the efficiency of machine learning-based colour reconstruction approaches. This metric measures the time taken to reconstruct an image, calculated by:

$$T_{reconstruction} = t_{end} - t_{start}$$

Efficiency in reconstruction time is critical for practical applications, especially when processing large datasets or requiring real-time processing. This ensures that the developed algorithms are both time-efficient and scalable.

Resource Utilization [KPI 3.3]:

Resource Utilization assesses the computational resources required for the reconstruction process. In PERCEIVE, it is measured through CPU/GPU usage and memory usage:

$$U_{CPU/GPU} = \frac{\text{Total CPU GPU time used}}{\text{Total available CPU GPU time}} \times 100\%$$

$$U_{memory} = \frac{\text{Memory used}}{\text{Total available memory}} \times 100\%$$

Efficient use of computational resources is essential for the practical deployment of the reconstruction algorithms, allowing for cost savings and enabling larger-scale applications.

User Satisfaction (Subjective Rating) [KPI 3.2]:

User Satisfaction is a qualitative metric that collects feedback from cultural heritage professionals on the perceived quality of the reconstructed images. In PERCEIVE, user satisfaction is measured using a Likert scale, where users rate the quality of reconstructed images on a scale from 1 to 5. The average satisfaction score is then calculated:

$$S_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N S_i}{N}$$

A satisfaction threshold of $\geq 90\%$ indicates that the tools developed meet the practical needs and expectations of the end-users. This metric ensures that the tools are user-centric and effective.

Just Noticeable Fade (JNF) [KPI 3.2]:

Just Noticeable Fade (JNF) is integrated as a sub-metric under User Satisfaction to assess the perceptibility of colour fading in reconstructed images. JNF represents the smallest change in colour that can be perceived as fading by an average observer. By incorporating JNF, the PERCEIVE project ensures that reconstructed images do not exhibit noticeable fading, which can detract from user satisfaction. Cultural heritage professionals provide feedback on whether the fading is perceptible and how it affects their overall satisfaction with the colour restoration process.

Just Noticeable Difference (JND) [KPI 3.2]:

Just Noticeable Difference (JND) is another crucial sub-metric under User Satisfaction, focusing on the perceptual accuracy of colour reconstruction. JND quantifies the minimum colour difference that can be perceived between two colours. In the context of the PERCEIVE project, JND is used to ensure that the differences between original and reconstructed colours remain below the perceptibility threshold. Feedback from users on the perceptibility of colour differences helps in fine-tuning the reconstruction process to achieve higher fidelity and improve overall user satisfaction.

Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [KPI 3.1]:

The Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) is a widely used metric for evaluating the perceived quality of reconstructed images. SSIM considers changes in structural information, luminance, and contrast, providing a measure that aligns closely with human visual perception. It is particularly useful for assessing the fidelity of colour reconstruction, ensuring that the restored images retain the visual characteristics of the original artifacts.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio - Blocking (PSNR-B) [KPI 3.1]:

PSNR-B is an extension of the traditional PSNR metric, designed to quantify the quality of image reconstruction with a focus on blocking artifacts. It measures the ratio between the maximum possible power of a signal and the power of corrupting noise, expressed in decibels. Higher PSNR-B values indicate better reconstruction quality. This metric is essential for comparing different reconstruction techniques and ensuring that the reconstructed images are of high fidelity.

Considerations on KPIs

The proposed metrics for the PERCEIVE project offer a comprehensive and multidimensional evaluation of machine learning-based colour reconstruction approaches. By integrating traditional metrics such as Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) and Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio - Blocking (PSNR-B) with specialized measures like Colour Difference (ΔE) and Edge Preservation Index (EPI), the project addresses both the technical and perceptual aspects critical for accurate colour restoration. These metrics ensure that reconstructed images meet high standards of visual fidelity while retaining the intricate details and structural integrity of the original artifacts. Efficiency-focused metrics such

as Reconstruction Time and Resource Utilization further guarantee that the developed tools are practical and scalable, making them suitable for real-world applications in the cultural heritage sector.

The inclusion of User Satisfaction as a qualitative metric underscores PERCEIVE's commitment to developing user-centric tools that meet the practical needs of cultural heritage professionals. This holistic approach, combining technical robustness with usability, ensures that the tools are effective in preserving and presenting cultural artifacts. Compared to state-of-the-art methods, the proposed metrics provide a more nuanced framework tailored to the unique challenges of colour reconstruction in cultural heritage.

Ultimately, the integration of these diverse and rigorous metrics into the evaluation framework underscores PERCEIVE's commitment to excellence in cultural heritage conservation. By ensuring the highest standards of accuracy, efficiency, and user satisfaction, the project stands to make a significant impact on the preservation and appreciation of cultural heritage artifacts, promoting their re-appropriation and ensuring their legacy for future generations.

4. PERCEIVE UX Evaluation General Strategy

4.1 Overview of the topic of evaluation

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

Generally, there are two categories of **evaluation models** that can be used when a user interacts with a multimedia product:

- The *objective measure* of human-machine interaction, of the user's experience with the product, such as initial performance, long-term performance, learnability, how much of what the system teaches us sticks in our heads and the use of advanced features;
- The *subjective measure* of human-machine interaction, such as the impressions that the user has of the system, long-term user satisfaction.

As already mentioned in Chapter 1, evaluations can be *formative* or *summative*, that is, anticipatory of the final product and useful for understanding how the ideation process is actually translating into a fully functional application; or conclusive and referable to the aspects of real usability and compliance with user needs.

In addition, evaluations are also characterized by the **evaluation methods** used: we speak of *qualitative or quantitative research*. We use both of them in PERCEIVE PROJECT.

The first is a type of empathic, empirical, exploratory, direct, and physical research. It is used to understand the reasons, motivations, opinions, and trends that lie behind the more numerical data of quantitative research. The most used techniques in this case are F2F (Face to Face), the so-called focus groups in which a very small sample of respondents (carefully selected participants) are interviewed for a very long time. The F2F is video-recorded and then transcribed as storytelling, in images or stories. Another technique is in-depth questionnaires, or open-ended questionnaires that allow the user to freely express their thoughts, doubts, or respond to a specific request or opinion, voluntarily and unconditionally.

Quantitative research, on the other hand, is used to quantify, using numerical data or in any case data that can then be easily transformed into statistics, and measures the behaviour, opinions, and attitudes of a very large sample of respondents. Let's say that to talk about "quantitative" you need to reach a sample of at least 50 people, but usually there are many more. Quantitative research can expand its scope by carrying out multi-country surveys, where the demographic and cultural aspect is also taken into consideration during the analysis of the results. The more data you get, the more precise the statistics will be. The methods of collecting quantitative data are mainly paper or online questionnaires, both lasting an average of 5-7 minutes. The questions often require a rating from 0 to 10 or multiple choice through a graphic symbol. You can measure the degree of satisfaction with a product or its usability or effectiveness. The data is then transcribed into numbers, graphs, statistics. Observations also partially fall into this category: they collect objective-subjective data from the users who are being monitored; their actions, gestures, glances and paths are recorded according to a pre-established form. Quantity, also in this case, is fundamental to obtain a credible and objectifiable resulting basis.

Evaluation procedures can then follow different approaches:

Continuous iteration. This procedure tends to maximize the effectiveness of the system/product and minimize the risk of errors. It allows for quantitative measures on the UX and metrics as

indicators of user performance. Furthermore, these evaluations are most often done in the laboratory, or in controlled environments, or are done in the field. This procedure includes an entire process of preparation, data collection, data analysis and report creation. The PERCEIVE PROJECT will benefit from this procedure.

Quick survey. This procedure is fast and cheap, but not always effective; it is useful in the early stages of processes when things happen quickly, such as evaluating the graphic interface, intra-section navigation, choosing the layout of the contents, etc. It is used a lot to have initial reactions and early feedback from users (often experts called ad hoc).

Empirical technique. It consists of using relevant data with observations on participants in the laboratory or in the field. Usually, the researcher does not place limits on the user's action, nor does he ask him to perform operations; he simply observes, to understand how the product behaves in daily use. It is essential, in field observation, that the researcher makes sure to make the effect of his presence irrelevant, or at least minimal; users must forget that they are being observed, to preserve the "ecological validity". For PERCEIVE PROJECT, this technique will be used, both in laboratory experiments and on the open-to-public venues.

Analytical technique. This is based on the observation of the intrinsic attributes of a multimedia application design, having Nielsen's heuristics grid available for the evaluation (Nielsen J., 1990; 1992; 1993). In the heuristic evaluation, the user interface plays a fundamental role. It is controlled by experts and its prototyping and development is evaluated by recording every time a heuristic aspect is violated. In the software development of a multimedia system, for example, the use of a heuristic approach can facilitate the implementation of a good user interface, allowing users to navigate a complex system intuitively and without difficulty. When necessary, the interface can guide users using tooltips (command descriptions), help buttons, invitations to chat with support, etc. For PERCEIVE PROJECT this technique will be used in laboratory experiments.

UX metrics are therefore the result of all the evaluations of the user experience of a product - in our case multimedia. The common goal is obviously to obtain good metrics to certify the success of the UX and of the product itself. In the case of the PERCEIVE PROJECT, these metrics will have to reflect the dynamics of Digital Cultural Heritage experience about colours' reconstruction. Furthermore, they will be influenced by the type of experience carried out, whether done alone or in a group.

4.2 Why measure UX? How to do it?

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

There are many reasons to measure the user experience: the main, and most important, is that you can identify problem areas and improve them in order to reach a level of satisfaction in the user that supports him in using the product made available to him. Furthermore, this data is useful to clearly define the positioning of the multimedia product in question (and a possible competitive advantage).

Several parameters are the basis of UX measurement. We consider:

- A. The analysis of user satisfaction **at test level** (*test level satisfaction*). This is of an exclusively technical nature but with a strong subjective component. An example is the functioning of a touchscreen application in the laboratory, to test its usability, specifically, the navigability and

visibility of icons and other graphic elements. For PERCEIVE PROJECT this type of analysis will certainly be used in the prototyping and implementation phases of the multimedia product, using ad hoc templates with both qualitative and quantitative evaluation indices.

- B. The analysis of user satisfaction **at the general activity level** (*task level satisfaction*). It is of a social nature, it examines cognitive-behavioural aspects. An example is the experience of an “interactive autochrome” inside a museum space, where the subject of the analysis is not only the technological apparatus but also its context of use and the anthropological feedback of the interviewee. For PERCEIVE PROJECT this type of analysis will certainly be used in the final phase of releasing the product/prototypes/tool to the public but also in the semi-final piloting phase at the temporary venue or real place of use.

In other words, the post-task evaluation helps to identify parts of the interface that have been particularly problematic, while the more in-depth post-study evaluation allows for an overall evaluation after the participants have had the opportunity to interact with the entire product (Tullis and Albert, 2008). The first is therefore focused more on the product, while the second on the type of users who evaluate its general usability.

4.2.1 Satisfaction at test level

The *Test level satisfaction* (A) is an evaluation made after the end of the experience of using the multimedia product. It measures the overall impression of the usability and global user experience. In this circumstance, learning and understanding of the contents are not evaluated, but only technical and aesthetic aspects. There are a series of validated questionnaires already used in the ICT and IxD fields that can also be taken into consideration for PERCEIVE PROJECT, such as:

- **System Usability Scale (SUS)**. The SUS questionnaire is used during tests to evaluate one of the main dimensions of the usability of a product: satisfaction, definable as the pleasure that the user feels in using a system. For each statement, participants must provide a degree of agreement on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 equal "not at all in agreement" and 5 equals "completely in agreement".
- **Click Test**. The first click test examines what a user selects/performs first on the interface to complete the intended task. It is a tracking of the sequence of their actions (of their clicks). It can be performed on a working website or interface, a prototype or a wireframe.
- **Eye Tracking**. Eye tracking involves measuring the position of the eye or the movement of the eye while an individual is viewing a web page/online portal or mobile app. When users are connected to eye tracking software, it can detect:
 - Where they are looking
 - How long they have been looking
 - How their focus moves from one element to another
 - What parts of the interface are missing
 - How they are navigating the length of the page
 - How the size and positioning of articles affect attention.

4.2.2 Satisfaction at the task level

Task level satisfaction (B) is an evaluation also made after the end of the experience of using the multimedia product or, in any case, after the cessation or conclusion of the assigned task. It is based

on short questionnaires and users should fill it in, for example, immediately after completing a specific task (even if the objective has not been achieved). These evaluations aim to measure and quantify how difficult it was to complete a certain task (activity) during a test. Among the most popular questionnaires used in these circumstances, there are:

- **After Scenario Questionnaire (ASQ).** The ASQ is a questionnaire composed of three statements, each of which is accompanied by a 7-point Likert scale [Allen E. & Seaman C., 2007]. The 3 statements are:
 - I am satisfied with the ease of completing the scenario.
 - I am satisfied with the time taken to complete the scenario.
 - I am satisfied with the support information (help, tooltip, messages) provided within the scenario.

Such a questionnaire will be used for PERCEIVE PROJECT because it is useful for quickly identifying discrepancies between the authors' conceptual assumptions and the expectations of end users.

- **Mental Effort Questionnaire (SMEQ).** The SMEQ is a questionnaire used to calculate subjective mental effort, through a single rating scale with a score from 0 to 150. Different labels are associated with the scale to make it easier for users to evaluate (for example, "quite difficult to do", "very difficult to do", etc.). The total mental effort is then calculated by adding all the SMEQ values for each user. For PERCEIVE PROJECT, SMEQ will be slightly adapted and simplified.
- **Usability Magnitude Estimation (UME).** This evaluation measures judgments related to the usability of a product based on the user's sensory stimuli. This process is adopted to evaluate the perceived difficulty during the performance of specific tasks and the percentage of effort that each task requires from the user, depending on their natural predispositions. The final goal of the UME is, in fact, to obtain a measure that estimates the relationship between user and task. Such a measure will be used for PERCEIVE PROJECT.
- **Single Easy Question-Task (SEQT).** This is the most suitable questionnaire to evaluate the level of post-task satisfaction, due to the ease of correlation with other usability parameters. It consists of the formulation of a single question after the task. The general objective of this type of questionnaire is to generate a quantitative measure of the user experience after completing a task, to evaluate its difficulty or complexity and compare it with other sets of tasks. An example is to ask the user, immediately after interacting with the multimedia system "How would you rate your experience?", "How do you think you interacted?" "Are you satisfied with how you acted?", answering with a rating on a scale of 1 to 5. For PERCEIVE PROJECT this evaluation will certainly be useful to highlight the user's perception during the experience, comparing it with the observations made by the researcher, to highlight any inconsistencies or confirm behavioural attitudes common to multiple users.
- **Contextual interview.** During these interviews, researchers watch and listen while users interact with the multimedia product, use it, trying to get the most benefit from it. Contextual interviews tend to be more natural and consequently sometimes more realistic, especially since they are carried out in places familiar to the user and in completely normal conditions. The questions are established a priori and include both open and closed questions/single or multiple choice. This evaluation technique will certainly be used for PERCEIVE PROJECT.

4.3 UX Evaluation roadmap

Alfonsina Pagano (CNR ISPC)

Conducting an evaluation means a) giving meaning to operations, actions, words, behaviours and procedures in relation to the objectives of the work team; b) comparing such data with a specific grid of evaluation indices, useful for defining the positioning of each data in terms of success or failure; c) finally, reflecting on what emerged from the evaluation to read such results in a contextual and objective manner, as well as d) aligning the desires of the work team with those of the target audience, to establish the positioning of the developed product in the market - of Digital Cultural Heritage field, in our case.

Evaluation is therefore a *scientific research methodology*, which follows a pre-established procedure and has precise phases to consider (Fig. 2). For PERCEIVE PROJECT we will refer to the below schema. A detailed description is reported in Del 7.2.

Fig. 2 - Roadmap of planning, conducting and analysing the evaluation of the user experience of a product/context of use.

However, planning is not simple and automatic since UX involves multiple disciplines, given the nature of the subject analysed (human capital) and of the analysing subject (technological product-service-prototype). Nonetheless, it follows a very specific work chain.

This type of evaluation is undoubtedly a subjective-analytical procedure (given the central role of the researcher or evaluator), which must respect these 3 simple rules:

- **Transparency in communicating evaluations**
- **Sharing of evaluation criteria**
- **Triangulation of points of view**

The evaluation is not placed at the end of any experiential path but accompanies it in the development of the product or experience.

4.3.1 UX Evaluation Planning

UX evaluation planning is the most important phase of the investigation process. This is because the choice of evaluation tools (1), the methods to be applied (2) for data collection, the times of submission to the user (3) and the context (4) where this activity is carried out, can greatly influence the outcomes.

As for the *tools* (1), these can be used individually or together with other investigative protocols, such as:

- Questionnaire
- Interview
- Observation
- Guided scenario
- Focus group
- Pilot test
- ...

The same applies to the chosen *investigative method* (2). Each of the evaluation protocols can indeed contain multiple items to investigate expressed in the form of:

- Single question + single answer
- Single question + multiple-choice answer
- Likert scale
- Gradient
- True/false affirmation
- Grid
- Thinking aloud
- Open questions
- Counting user actions
- Counting user errors
- Picture recognition
- ...

Furthermore, the method certainly arises from the objectives that one wants to investigate and from the theories of scientific research that are referred to, with respect to the academic background of the work team (i.e. ICT, humanities, computer science-engineering, etc.).

The *times of submission* of the evaluation (3) depend instead on 4 factors:

- Time available to the researcher to conduct the investigation
- Time available to user related both to (a) the “situated” user experience, designed for him when he interacts with the product, and (b) to the experiential path that leads the user to that specific product, after having used/seen/interacted with something else
- Length of the evaluation protocol, which should not usually exceed two pages, must consist of a different degree of complexity of the questions, have open questions, multiple choices, true / false and make use of images to lighten the reading and compiling (in the case of self-compiled questionnaires); finally, have a clear and not too small fonts and layouts

- Logistics of submission of the evaluation protocol, which can be carried out immediately after the interaction with the product, or after some time so as not to interfere with the overall experience of the user; can be carried out by a single user or in a group, taking care of recording the feedback and/or answers in a clear and evident manner (Who answered what? Did everyone agree? Is it the opinion of just one member of the group or of everyone?).

With respect to the *context of submission* (4), this also greatly influences the effectiveness of the evaluation. Studying exactly where to conduct the UX investigation is important; the researcher's position should not be underestimated either, as he must appear "invisible" but still recognizable and credible when interacting with the user. The evaluation can take place:

- Next to the multimedia product
- In an area separate from the multimedia product
- Standing / in a passage area
- Seated / in a relaxation and cool-down area
- A secluded, silent place
- A crowded place, full of voices and environmental noises
- Single researcher or more than one.

All this therefore leads to the *structuring of the evaluation tools* (again 1). Generally, when talking about observation protocols, questionnaires and guided scenarios, the composition is more or less the same:

- Demographic data are always collected, at the beginning of the protocol or at the end of it, in order to contextualize the answers and/or observations collected
- A central part of the evaluation refers to the issues that you want to investigate, in the form of open or closed questions, quizzes or other tools and methods illustrated above
- A final part instead concerns aspects of general user satisfaction, deriving from free comments, open or closed questions.

The protocols thus defined can at this point be translated into paper materials or carried out via online services. The latter can provide various investigative solutions:

- *online template + online automatically-generated responses*, the evaluation protocol is built online but the responses are automatically generated by the online service depending on the actions of the user who compiles it; it is administered via mobile device or directly online
- *online template + offline responses*, the evaluation protocol is built online but can be compiled offline, via mobile device; the data is sent to the server as soon as there is a wifi connection
- *offline template + online responses*, the evaluation protocol is also built offline and can be compiled online, making it public on the web and/or sending it to users via mail.

4.3.2 Field data collection and transcription

When reporting the results of a UX evaluation, it is necessary to focus primarily on the transcription of the data, which differ in terms of the levels of success and failure. Including contextual information, explicitly citing the source, noting any external influences and presenting

sufficient details so that the “atmosphere” of the evaluation is identifiable, are all very important to recall some passages later. It is advisable to use tables to display the metrics and use graphs and visual elements to highlight trends, variances and inconsistencies when possible.

4.3.3 Analysis of the UX evaluation data

After the transcription of the collected data, we move on to the analysis and interpretation phase. This moment, like the definition of the evaluation methodology, is crucial for the reliability of scientific research.

Once the data have been checked, and redundancies and mistakes fixed, graphics can be produced: charts, graphs, histograms, diagrams, and tables are useful tools to read though collected data, giving shape to words and behaviours.

The discussion phase can start among the team, carefully reading each graphic in their singularity and in relation to the other metrics established at the beginning of the activity, looking for patterns and repeated items. What needs to emerge are:

- The descriptions of the activities (tasks)/questions with the highest and lowest completion rates; provide a summary of the completion percentages of successful activities per participant, activity and average success rate
- The average time taken to complete each activity
- The comments of the participants, which are always interesting as they are spontaneous and unplanned
- The reporting of the severity levels of issues emerging from the evaluation
- The recommendations suggested by the users in free form.

4.3.4 Applying UX Evaluation Results

To be valuable and reliable, UX evaluation needs to push the team to use what learned to improve the digital product-service-prototype, through an iterative and efficient process. It may not be possible to implement all recommendations. Developing a digital product is a series of trade-offs that balance between schedule, budget, team availability, and necessary changes. If it is not always possible to implement all recommendations, develop priorities based on solving the most recognizable and urgent issues.

5. PERCEIVE evaluation strategy model: a proposal

According to PERCEIVE goals, here is a first draft of the **UX evaluation model** which matches KPIs, supposed outcomes - *tools, prototypes and services developed by partners* - and evaluation initiatives.

The evaluation model incorporates relevant **types of assessment, techniques and methods**. It also uses different **outcomes, interaction types, cognitive and aesthetic aspects**, and **demographic analysis** to comprehensively assess user experience, usability, accuracy, and system design.

Goal	PERCEIVE Outcome(s)	Evaluation Objectives
(a) Increase sense of wonder and develop care	O1 - Know-How webinars O14 - Caring Prototype O16 - Design Toolbox	Measure emotional impact, engagement level, and development of "care" and curiosity for colour preservation.
(b) Train perception and awareness	O2 - Colour reconstruction guidelines O4 - Colour Knowledge Repository O7 - Colour Prediction Service	Evaluate user understanding of colour science and methodologies, retention of information, and educational effectiveness.
(c) Strengthen authenticity in remote experiences	O12 - Web3D multi-texture editor O13 - Authenticity Prototype O5 - PERCEIVE API	Assess user perception of authenticity in remote or digital experiences, visual and interactive realism, and user immersion.
(d) Widen access through participation	O15 - Open Museum Prototype O3 - Museum tools O6 - Colour Regeneration Service	Measure accessibility for diverse audiences, usability in digital and in-person formats, and satisfaction with participatory tools.

2.1 Goals recap

The PERCEIVE goals are declared in the Grant Agreement; they are carefully designed to elevate public engagement and foster a profound connection with Europe's coloured heritage collections.

The first objective is to **enhance the "sense of wonder"** among diverse audiences, cultivating a sustained sense of care and responsibility for these cultural assets. By sparking admiration and curiosity, PERCEIVE aims to foster a collective awareness of the significance and fragility of these collections.

Secondly, PERCEIVE seeks to **train and refine visitors' perception** by promoting a nuanced understanding of coloured collections, underpinned by an appreciation of the scientific processes involved in their preservation and restoration. This objective is geared toward building informed audiences who can grasp the complexities and importance of colour science in cultural heritage.

A third objective is to **strengthen the authenticity of remote experiences**, allowing digital engagements with heritage artifacts to convey a realistic and immersive quality. This will enable those who cannot access collections in person to have meaningful interactions with digital reproductions that faithfully reflect the original objects.

Finally, PERCEIVE wants to **widening access through participatory frameworks**, ensuring that audiences from varied backgrounds can actively engage with these collections. This goal emphasizes inclusivity and broad participation, supporting the creation of experiences that are accessible, educational, and impactful across a broad spectrum of society.

Goals
(a) increase the “sense of wonder” for coloured collections and develop a sense of “care”;
(b) train visitors' perception to promote better understanding of coloured collections and bring an awareness of the scientific process behind;
(c) strengthen “authenticity” in remote experiences;
(d) widen access through participation.

2.2 Outcomes

The PERCEIVE project is developing a comprehensive suite of outcomes aimed at advancing the understanding, preservation, and public engagement with coloured cultural heritage collections. These outcomes can be grouped into **4 categories**, each addressing specific aspects of the project’s overarching goals:

- knowledge dissemination
- technical tools and services
- visual and analytical tools
- innovative prototypes for enhanced user experience.

Each outcome can be a tool, a service or a prototype (*see D7.1*).

Relationship and differences between tool, service, prototype and demonstrator in PERCEIVE.

The list is continuously updated according to partners’ technological development and GANTT of WP6 and WP7.

PERCEIVE outcome(s) <i>(updated to June 2024)</i>
Knowledge Dissemination and Training
O1 – Know-How webinars and streaming lectures
O2 – Colour reconstruction methodology and guidelines
O3 – Tools and guidelines for museums and exhibition/light designers
Technical Tools and Services

O5 – PERCEIVE API
O6 – Colour Reconstruction and Regeneration Service
O7 – Colour Prediction Service
O8 – Colour restoration and colorization of B&W images
Visual and Analytical Tools
O4 – Colour Knowledge Repository
O9 – Analytical visualization
O10 – Light damage estimator
O11 – 3D model optimiser
O12 – web3d multi-texture interactive visualization editor service
Innovative Prototypes for Enhanced User Experience
O13 – Authenticity Prototype
O14 – Caring Prototype
O15 – Open Museum Prototype
O16 – Design Toolbox
O... - new in

2024

September 2024 Color rectification of artworks' images on chromogenic film		
September 2024 Color-mosaic/silver-image layer separation for Autochromes		
September 2024 Pan-/Ortho-chromatization of Hyperspectral cubes		
June 2024 Light Damage Estimator (O10)		
August 2024 2D Inpainting Service		
September 2024 Color rectification of artworks' images on chromogenic film		

List of *OUTCOMES*: supposed tools, services and prototypes developed within PERCEIVE project timeline.

2.3 Type of Assessment

The PERCEIVE outcomes’ assessment focuses on several key aspects to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness and impact of tools, services, and prototypes.

User Experience (A) is a primary area, exploring how people interact with and perceive each tool or service. This will include measuring ease of use, emotional engagement, and overall satisfaction. Another focal point will be the *Interaction with the system*, assessed based on established Nielsen/Norman usability principles. This evaluation will ensure the system is intuitive, provides helpful feedback, and supports efficient and seamless interactions.

PERCEIVE will also examine the *aesthetic aspects of the system*, focusing on the clarity and appeal of its visual interfaces. Visibility and layout will be considered to determine how they contribute to an engaging and visually coherent experience. Additionally, the *cognitive sphere* will be assessed to gauge users’ levels of attention, memory retention, and depth of understanding from their interactions. This will help in understanding how well the content supports learning and user engagement.

To better understand the accessibility and inclusivity of the tools, *demographics* will also be gathered, capturing users’ backgrounds such as age, cultural familiarity, and profession.

On the technical side, we will evaluate *core features of each tool or service (B)* to ensure they meet expectations and function as intended. *Usability* will be measured to identify how effectively users can operate the tools without encountering obstacles. The *accuracy of outputs*, like image quality and other performance metrics, will be a critical criterion, especially in tools where visual precision is essential. Lastly, *appearance Consistency* across different imaging technologies will be reviewed to confirm that the visual experience remains stable and reliable, regardless of the device used.

This assessment structure will ensure that each tool or service is both user-friendly and technically sound, aligning with PERCEIVE's high standards for quality and engagement.

Type of Assessment
<i>A. User experience of people using the tool/service/prototype</i>
Interaction with the system (Nielsen/Norman principles)
Aesthetical aspects of the system (Visibility)
Cognitive sphere (Attention, memorization and elaboration of the user experience)
Demographics
<i>B. Tool/service/prototype main features</i>
Usability of the system
Output accuracy (i.e., image quality, metrics....)
Appearance consistency across imaging technologies

2.4 Evaluation initiatives

The PERCEIVE project has planned a series of **UX evaluation initiatives** to capture feedback from users engaging with the project’s tools, services, and prototypes in diverse cultural and **exhibition settings, as well as in labs**. Below are the planned evaluation events:

PUBLIC OCCASIONS

1. General CHARE Scale - Bologna, ended in December 2024

This evaluation initiative is being carried out in the framework of the project in collaboration with the Department of Psychology of the University of Bologna (Prof Nori) and of the University of Rome La Sapienza (Prof. Piccardi, Dr Von Gal). This study aims at defining a first scale to assess general public sense of care towards Cultural Heritage (CHARE), adopting the Rasch model. It consists of a survey where citizens are questioned about behaviours adopted by citizens in the last year towards cultural heritage or sites

in Bologna will focus on gathering feedback from participants engaged in the broader CARE program. The primary goal of this session will be to assess how effectively PERCEIVE prototypes foster a "sense of care" among users for cultural heritage collections. The evaluation will involve targeted user surveys, focus group discussions, and individual interviews, all designed to capture both qualitative and quantitative insights into participants' emotional engagement and perception of cultural preservation responsibilities. Key areas of analysis will include user satisfaction, emotional impact, and cognitive engagement with the prototypes.

2. User Experience Evaluation at InArt exhibit and workshop - Oslo, MUNCH June 2024

During the InArt exhibit and workshop held at the MUNCH Museum in Oslo, PERCEIVE will conduct a specialized evaluation session to gauge user interactions with and reactions to specific tools and methodologies showcased within this event. This evaluation will include real-time observation, usability testing, and participant surveys, following methodologies detailed in D7.2 and further elaborated in a forthcoming specific report. The feedback will focus on the ease of use, perceived authenticity of digital representations, and participants’ appreciation of the scientific processes involved in colour restoration and conservation, providing valuable insights into the accessibility and educational impact of the PERCEIVE tools in a public exhibit setting.

3. User Experience Evaluation at Parcour Exhibit - Rotkreuz, Switzerland, HSLU, December 2024

The Parcour exhibit in Rotkreuz, Switzerland (HSLU) will serve as a unique occasion for a focused user experience (UX) evaluation in open air. It transforms the model of the traditional museum or gallery visit into an adventurous exploration, making the act of moving between exhibited work as significant as viewing the artworks themselves. The parcour features a set of science demonstrators designed to showcase ongoing research and the intricate technologies driving the PERCEIVE project, particularly its advancements in colour research. By offering an immersive and tangible experience of the technological innovations in the PERCEIVE project, visitors can engage with the project's achievements and see how the exhibit contributes to its dissemination in a truly novel manner. The evaluation will incorporate UX testing based on Nielsen/Norman principles, alongside cognitive assessments to measure the impact on users' attention, memory retention, and engagement. Structured feedback through surveys and post-interaction interviews will help identify any usability challenges and areas for improvement, particularly around the accuracy and visual appeal of PERCEIVE's digital reproductions in a professional exhibition environment.

4. Final PERCEIVE Exhibit Evaluation - Naples, November 2025

In the final PERCEIVE exhibit in Naples, scheduled for November 2025, a comprehensive UX and impact evaluation will be conducted. This final evaluation will gather detailed feedback on the overall user journey and the effectiveness of PERCEIVE's outcomes in promoting awareness, understanding, and appreciation of colour heritage. Through a combination of demographic analysis, structured UX feedback, and satisfaction metrics, this evaluation will explore how successfully the project's outcomes meet its goals of widening access, strengthening authenticity in remote experiences, and instilling a sense of wonder and care. The evaluation findings will be synthesized into an overarching report that highlights the strengths of the project's impact while offering actionable insights for future developments in digital cultural heritage.

LAB ACTIVITIES

The laboratory activities are designed to evaluate how accurately the reproductions of artworks reflect the originals, with a focus on specific viewing conditions typical of traditional display environments, such as museums or theatre settings, as well as those used in events organized by the PERCEIVE project.

Prototypes developed for upcoming events, including the Parcour Exhibit and the Final PERCEIVE Exhibit Evaluation, will undergo thorough metrological assessment. This evaluation, centred on spectrophotometric measurements, will determine the accuracy of the reproductions—a critical factor in preserving the authenticity of the viewer's experience.

This process will involve recreating the original visualization conditions within the laboratory and taking spectrophotometric measurements that match the observer's viewing environment. Additionally, the analysis will account for the complexity of human visual perception, applying colour appearance models to address potential mismatches in viewing conditions.

The final authenticity assessment will consider various parameters related to spectroradiometry, psychophysics, and visual perception to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the reproduction's fidelity to the original artwork.

These evaluations can be done in the controlled laboratory environment. In the PERCEIVE project they consist of calibration of colour devices such as monitors and projectors, and subjective image quality, specifically for the task of colour reconstruction.

5. Calibration of colour devices

Colour calibration of devices is a critical process to ensure that colours are displayed accurately and consistently across different screens and projectors. This involves adjusting the colour settings of a device to match a known standard. During calibration, a colorimeter or spectrophotometer measures the colours produced by the device, and the software adjusts the device's colour profile accordingly. This process helps to correct any deviations in colour reproduction, ensuring that the results displayed across devices match.

6. Subjective image quality Colour reconstruction

Subjective image quality for the task of colour reconstruction involves psychophysical experiments, playing a crucial role in understanding how to accurately restore and reproduce colours in the proposed scenarios. These experiments involve presenting subjects with both original and restored images to evaluate the effectiveness of different virtual restoration algorithms. Different parameters may be manipulated to generate multiple, possible restorations, and see how these factors affect the perception of restored colours.

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